

ON THE BITTER PRINCIPLES OF *CITRUS DECUMANA*

BY (MISS) ASIMA MOOKERJEE.

Two bitter principles, isomeric with each other and having the formula, $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$, have been isolated from the seeds of *Citrus decumana*. One of these has proved to be identical with limonin, while the other appears to be a new compound and has been called *neolimonin*. Alkali treatment of neolimonin furnished hexahydrolimoninic acid and another compound, which may be identical with *isolimonin* originally described by Koller and Czerny. A comparative study of the colour reactions of neolimonin, limonin and *isolimonin* has been made. Hexahydrolimoninic acid has been obtained in a crystalline form for the first time.

The bitter principles of Citrus seeds have been investigated rather extensively. As early as 1841 Bernay (*Annalen*, 1841, **40**, 317) isolated from the seeds of many species of Citrus (*C. aurantium*, Risso, *C. limonum*, Risso, and *C. bigardia*, Loisl) a very bitter substance which he named limonin. He erroneously thought it to be an alkaloid. Three years later Schmidt (*Annalen*, 1844, **51**, 388) showed that Bernay's limonin was not a basic substance and that it resembled columbin, isolated from the root of *Jateorrhiza palmata* by Wittstock (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1830, **19**, 298). Schmidt, moreover, found that limonin, $C_{22}H_{26}O_7$, (m.p. 242°) was physiologically inactive. Since then other workers have studied its properties and reactions (Paterno and Oglialoro, *Ber.*, 1879, **12**, 685; Peters and Frerich, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1902, **240**, 661).

Peters and Frerich purified limonin by alkali treatment and recorded the m. p. 275° . Recently Koller and Czerny (*Monatsh.*, 1936, **67**, 248; 1937, **70**, 26) have reported the results of a more elaborate investigation of limonin, $C_{23}H_{26}O_7$ (m. p. 280°) isolated from orange pips. They isolated a second bitter substance, $C_{23}H_{28}O_7$ (m. p. 264°), from the same source which they named *isolimonin*. Shortly thereafter Feist and Schulte (*Ber.*, 1936, **69**, 1322) isolated from lemon seeds a third bitter substance, named citrolimonin, m. p. 304° , for which they advanced the molecular formula $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$. Similarity in equivalent weight and specific rotation of citrolimonin and limonin have led Koller and Czerny to believe these two compounds to be identical, despite a considerable discrepancy in the reported melting points. Koller and Czerny suggested that the lower melting point

of their limonin might be due to the use of alkali during isolation and purification, a suggestion which the present worker has been unable to support (*vide infra*).

In a recent communication Higby (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 3013) reported the isolation of two bitter lactones, namely limonin, $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$ (m.p. 290° , decomp.) from Valencia orange and *isolimonin*, $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$ (m.p. 264° , decomp.) from Washington Navel orange. From analytical and other data he concluded that his limonin was identical with the citrolimonin of Feist and Schulte and the limonin of Koller and Czerny. As regards his *isolimonin*, Higby did not establish its identity with Koller and Czerny's *isolimonin* but the similarity in melting point and other properties was emphasised.

The present investigation has been undertaken with a view to isolate the bitter principles of the seeds of a variety of *Citrus decumana* (N.O. Rutacæ), known locally as *Bâtávi*. From the air-dried seeds two colourless crystalline bitter substances, besides a thick pale yellow oil, have been isolated. These bitter principles have been purified *without* treatment with alkali and many of their properties have been studied. One of the constituents (m.p. 280° , decomp.; yield 0.23%) has been found to be identical with Higby's limonin by a direct comparison which has been made possible through the kindness of Dr. R. H. Higby, to whom the authoress is greatly indebted. The second bitter constituent (m.p. $240-42^\circ$, decomp.; yield 0.15%) has been found to be a new compound and has consequently been named *neolimonin*.

Neolimonin, $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -111^\circ$ (acetone), yields a phenylhydrazone, m.p. $215-20^\circ$, whereas a yellow osazone, m.p. $221-25^\circ$, has been obtained from *isolimonin* (Higby, *loc. cit.*). *Neolimonin* has no methoxy and methylenedioxy groups. On acetylation *neolimonin* gives what is regarded as an anhydrodiacetyl derivative (m.p. $219-20^\circ$, decomp.) whereas *isolimonin* furnishes a diacetyl derivative, the m. p. of which has not been recorded (Koller and Czerny, *loc. cit.*).

It has been observed by Higby that boiling hydrochloric acid converts *isolimonin* into limonin and hexahydrolimoninic acid. Under similar experimental conditions *neolimonin* is partially converted into hexahydrolimoninic acid. Alkali treatment, however, gives the same acid and another neutral product, m. p. 262° (decomp.). The physical properties of the latter agree with those of *isolimonin* which have been reported to melt at 264° , (decomp.) (Higby) and $262-64^\circ$ (decomp.) (Koller and Czerny). The

analytical data (C, 63.0; H, 7.0%), however, are not in agreement with those of *isolimonin* which requires C, 66.3 and H, 6.43 per cent. Further considerations about its molecular composition are postponed partly on account of the poor yield and partly for want of an authentic specimen of *isolimonin* of Koller and Czerny.

Hexahydrolimonic acid was obtained by Higby as an amorphous, light coloured, globular aggregate, m. p. 175.77° and by Koller and Czerny as an amorphous substance which passed into crystalline state, m.p. 178°, on keeping in contact with water. It has now been found that the acid crystallises from acetone and has m. p. 201.3°. No marked difference in the analytical data between the two varieties are noticed and the m. p. of the amorphous variety is not depressed by admixture with the crystalline variety in equal proportions. Contrary to the experience of Koller and Czerny the methyl ester of hexahydrolimonic acid has also been obtained in a crystalline condition, m. p. 173.4°.

Limonin remains unaffected by acid or alkali treatment and must, therefore, be considered as the most stable of the three compounds. The relationship between limonin, *isolimonin* and neolimonin is indicated below :

Since *isolimonin* has a melting point intermediate between the melting points of limonin and neolimonin, it was thought that it might be a mixture of the last two compounds. The presence of one-third molecule of alcohol of crystallisation in *isolimonin*, on this assumption, would correspond to a mixture of limonin and neolimonin in the ratio of 6:1. In fact a mixture of limonin (6 parts) and neolimonin (1 part) melted indefinitely between 233° and 271° and the mixture on crystallisation gave products which melted at 256.74° (first crop), 253.72° (second crop) and 248.52° (third crop). No product with a sharp m.p. of 262° could be isolated. Therefore, *isolimonin* cannot be regarded as a mixture of limonin and neolimonin. It has, moreover, been observed that the m.p. of neolimonin is depressed by admixture either with limonin or *isolimonin*. The colour reactions of the three compounds, as given below, also prove that they are different from one another.

Colour Reactions of Neolimonin, isoLimonin and Limonin.

Reagents or Reactions.	Limonin.	Neolimonin.	isoLimonin.
Concentrated sulphuric acid	Deep red soln.	Same	Same
Concentrated sulphuric acid + anisaldehyde	Purple	Purple	At first a pinkish tinge turning red
Concentrated sulphuric acid + $K_2Cr_2O_7$	Red, then pale yellow, finally green	Red, then quickly green.	Red, then slowly green
Erdmann's reagent	Yellow, then almost colourless	Red	Deep red
Fröhde's reagent	Red, then black	Yellow, then red	Red, and finally black
Mandelin's reagent	Red, then deep green	Greenish yellow, green, then rapidly yellow	Yellow with greenish tinge, then deep yellow, finally black
<i>o</i> -Dinitrobenzene (alkaline)	Dirty purple, then red	Same	Same
Liebermann's reaction	(i) H_2SO_4 -layer : pale orange (ii) CCl_4 -layer : colourless	(i) Yellow (ii) Pink	(i) Purple; then red (ii) Colourless
Liebermann—Burchard's reaction	$CHCl_3$ -layer : colourless (ii) H_2SO_4 -layer : pink, yellow, then black	(i) Same (ii) Purple, then orange	(i) Same (ii) Yellow, then red
Salkowski's reaction	(i) H_2SO_4 -layer : yellow (ii) $CHCl_3$ -layer : colourless	Same	Same
Lifschutz reaction	(i) H_2SO_4 -layer : pink (ii) $CHCl_3$ -layer : purplish (Pink ring at junction)	(i) Same (ii) Same	(i) Same (ii) Same
Rosenheim's reaction	(i) H_2SO_4 -layer : colourless (ii) $CHCl_3$ -layer : colourless	Same	Same

It is interesting to note that Higby had obtained a compound, m.p. 240-42° (decomp.), from Navel orange, which he considered to be impure *isolimonin* and obtained pure *isolimonin* from it after treatment with alkali. It has been established in course of the present investigation that *neolimonin*

undergoes transformation into *isolimonin* under the influence of alkali. It is, therefore, very likely that *isolimonin* is not present as such in Navel orange, but is a secondary product derived from *neolimonin*. The same remark also applies to the occurrence of *isolimonin* in orange seeds as observed by Koller and Czerny. This hypothesis, however, needs further verification.

The structural relationship between *limonin*, *neolimonin* and *isolimonin* is not very clear. Although *limonin* has been subjected to chemical investigation for nearly a century, no structural formula for the substance has been advanced. Recent workers, however, agree that it contains two lactone groups, and Koller and Czerny suggested that *limonin* may be related to *columbin* and hence to cardiac aglucones. The present worker has been able to account for many of the reactions of *limonin* on the basis of this hypothesis, but rigid chemical evidence has yet to be adduced in its support.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Limonin and Neolimonin.—The seeds of *C. decumana* (2 kg.), collected in the locality, were coarsely powdered and extracted with petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) in a Soxhlet for 6-8 hours to remove the major part of the oil, and then extracted with benzene during 24 hours. The pale yellow benzene extract was concentrated on the water-bath under reduced pressure to about 100 c.c., when crystals of *limonin* and *neolimonin* separated out. The crude product (12 g.) was collected, washed with cold benzene (40 c.c.) to remove fatty matters, and then slowly crystallised from acetone (100-150 c.c.). The crystals consisted of opaque star-shaped aggregates of *limonin* and transparent rods of *neolimonin*. The two types of crystals were separated from each other mechanically, and the two fractions were repeatedly crystallised from acetone till the m.p. of *limonin* (yield 4.5 g.) became constant at 230° and that of *neolimonin* (yield 3 g.) at 240-42°.

Limonin crystallises from acetone in thick rhombic plates or from alcohol in thin shining flakes. It crystallises from acetic acid with one molecule of acetic acid, although it has no tendency to combine with alcohol or acetone. A chloroform solution of *limonin* easily discharges the colour of bromine. *Limonin* also combines with one molecule of phenylhydrazine.

Neolimonin dissolves freely in chloroform and pyridine; it is fairly soluble in acetone but sparingly in alcohol, and insoluble in ether, petroleum ether and water. The crystals are transparent when crystallised

from acetone. They become opaque when kept exposed to air for a few days evidently due to the loss of acetone or crystallisation. Acetone is completely removed on drying at $120-25^{\circ}$ in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for a few hours. Alcohol of crystallisation is, however, not lost so easily. A specimen, crystallised from alcohol and dried for 3 hours at 100° in *vacuo*, gave on analysis: C, 63.50; H, 7.00. $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$, $2C_2H_5OH$ requires C, 64.03; H, 7.4 per cent. Another specimen, crystallised from acetone, was dried to constant weight in *vacuo* at $120-25^{\circ}$. (Found: loss in weight, 10.93. $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$, Me_2CO requires 10.98 %. Found in a dry specimen: C, 65.80; H, 6.7. $C_{26}H_{30}O_8$ requires C, 66.30; H, 6.43 per cent).

Neolimonin (0.2973 g.), dissolved in acetone (50 c.c.), showed a rotation of -0.66° in 1 dm. tube at 33° . Hence $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -111^{\circ}$.

Acetylation of Neolimonin.—A mixture of neolimonin (0.1 g.), acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine was gently boiled for 4 hours. The liquid products of the reaction were removed under reduced pressure and the brown residue taken up with acetone, charcoaled and filtered. After a week, the solution, which exhibited a green fluorescence, deposited a small quantity of pale yellow plates, which became colourless after three crystallisations from acetone, and had m.p. $219-20^{\circ}$. (Found in sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 100° for 3 hours: C, 67.34; H, 6.5. $C_{30}H_{32}O_8$ requires C, 67.16; H, 6.0 per cent).

Phenylhydrazone of Neolimonin.—Neolimonin (0.2 g.) was refluxed in alcoholic solution with freshly distilled phenylhydrazine (0.3 g.) and glacial acetic acid (0.3 c.c.) on the water-bath for 3 hours. The yellow solution was freed from alcohol under diminished pressure and the residue taken up with 80% alcohol (15 c.c.) and concentrated. The yellow amorphous precipitate was collected next day and washed with cold alcohol (20 c.c.), m.p. $215-20^{\circ}$. (Found in specimen dried at $120-25^{\circ}$ for 3 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : N, 4.60. $C_{32}H_{36}O_7N_2$ requires N, 5.00 per cent).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on Neolimonin.—Pure neolimonin (0.7 g.), dissolved in acetone (35 c.c.) was refluxed with 6*N*-hydrochloric acid (7 c.c.) on the water-bath for 6 hours. After neutralisation with lead carbonate the solution was filtered, concentrated, diluted with water and again heated when a brown viscous mass separated out. This was collected and after treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution, was crystallised from acetone and found to be unchanged neolimonin. The bicarbonate solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, the precipitate was collected, washed with a little ice-cold water and after drying in a desiccator (calcium chloride), was purified by repeated dissolution in sodium bicarbonate and precipitation with hydrochloric acid; m.p. $175-77^{\circ}$. (Found in a specimen dried at 100°

for 3 hours, in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 62.60; H, 7.8. $C_{26}H_{38}O_6$ requires C, 63.1; H, 7.69 per cent). The hexahydrolimoninic acid described above (0.0616 g.), dissolved in acetone (25 c.c.), showed a rotation of -0.085° in a 0.5 dcm. tube. Hence $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -69^\circ$. Higby records $[\alpha]_D^{22} = -70^\circ$ for the amorphous acid.

Crystalline Hexahydrolimoninic Acid.—The above acid was repeatedly crystallised from acetone when it formed colourless shining rods, m.p. 201-3°. (Found in a specimen dried for 3 hours at 135-40° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 63.42; H, 7.33. $C_{26}H_{38}O_6$ requires C, 63.10; H, 7.69 per cent). The crystalline acid showed $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -74.3^\circ$ (acetone).

Action of Alkali on Neolimonin.—A clear solution of neolimonin (0.18 g.) in aqueous potassium hydroxide (10 c.c. of 13%) was acidified with hydrochloric acid after standing for 2 hours at room temperature. The precipitate was collected, and washed with ice-cold water, when a part (0.09 g.) became insoluble in bicarbonate solution. From the filtrate an amorphous precipitate (0.08 g.) was isolated after acidification. Purified by dissolution in sodium bicarbonate and acidification with hydrochloric acid, and finally by crystallising from acetone (till the m.p. became constant) colourless needles (identified as hexahydrolimoninic acid), m.p. 201-3°, were obtained. (Found in specimen dried at 135-40° for 2 hours in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 : C, 63.42; H, 7.33. $C_{26}H_{38}O_6$ requires C, 63.10; H, 7.69 per cent).

The insoluble residue (0.09 g., referred to above) was thrice crystallised from alcohol when thick plates, m.p. 262° (decomp.) (unaltered by further crystallisation) were obtained. When heated to 140° it turned opaque, became an opaque powder at 225-235° and finally melted at 262° with decomposition. Crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and benzene it had the same m.p., but did not show the heat changes as recorded above showing that the former specimen had alcohol of crystallisation. Dried to constant weight in *vacuo* at 135° it gave C, 63.0; H, 7.0 per cent. This substance may be isolimonin.

Methyl Ester of Hexahydrolimoninic Acid.—Hexahydrolimoninic acid (0.04 g.), dissolved in pure methyl alcohol, was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane and the mixture left for 20 hours at room temperature. The residue left after removal of the solvents crystallised from benzene, when colourless transparent plates, m.p. 173-74°, were obtained. These, however, soon lost their transparency and became opaque apparently due to loss of solvent of crystallisation. Koller and Czerny had obtained an amorphous methyl ester of the acid, the m.p. of which has not been recorded.

Limonin.—Limonin, m.p. 280° (decomp.), isolated from *C. decumana* was dried at 120° for 3 hours in *vacuo* over P₂O₅. (Found: C, 65.87; H, 6.24. C₂₀H₃₀O₈ requires C, 66.30; H, 6.43 per cent). The substance (0.398 g.), dissolved in acetone (25 c.c.), showed a rotation of -3.54° in 1.89 dcm. tube at 33°, whence $[\alpha]_D^{33} = -117^\circ$. (Higby records -106°, -108° and -114° at 20° in acetone depending upon the source of limonin). Mixed m.p. of limonin with Higby's compound was found to be 279-80° (decomp.).

Phenylhydrazone of Limonin.—Limonin furnished an amorphous reddish phenylhydrazone, m.p. 250-55°, when the experimental conditions described under neolimonin phenylhydrazone were followed. (Found in a specimen dried for 2 hours at 120° in *vacuo* over P₂O₅: N, 5.3; C₃₂H₄₆O₇N₂ requires N, 5.00 per cent).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on Limonin.—Limonin (0.5 g.), dissolved in acetone (25 c.c.), was refluxed with 6*N*-hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) for 6 hours on the water-bath. The solution was worked up as described before in the case of neolimonin. The crystalline precipitate (0.5 g.) in this case was entirely insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, and formed heavy plates, m.p. 280° (decomp.), after two crystallisations from acetone and was identified as unchanged material by a direct comparison.

Action of Alkali on Limonin.—Limonin (0.2 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide (10 c.c. of 13%) and the clear solution kept for 48 hours. The precipitate (0.195 g.), obtained on acidifying the solution, did not dissolve at all in sodium bicarbonate solution, and the filtrate showed a blue fluorescence. The precipitate crystallised from alcohol in shining flakes, m.p. 280° (decomp.), not depressed by admixture with limonin.

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